

A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT, PRICE AND BRAND IMAGE ON AYURVEDA PRODUCTS BY CONSUMERS

Anilkumar.R

Faculty of Management, ISME, Bangalore.

Introduction

Ayurveda is a science of life with a holistic approach to health and personalized medicine. Ayurveda is considered to be one of the oldest natural healing therapy and medical science using herbs, tree roots, branches, stems and other natural available ingredients. The benefits and scope of Ayurveda is enormous and still growing with the research in treating many ailments such as blood pressure, arthrities, asthma, cancer, paralytic attack and many more. Due to the availability of processed food and chemical based food, humans are infected by many diseases. This consumption of processed food with chemical is in raise even in all the economies of scale as it is available at cheaper price and even costlier with the brand tag for rich class consumption.

Hence this research has become evident to understand how the influence of awareness of Ayurveda product, awareness of price and brand image on their purchasing decision of Ayurveda products. Where 251 respondents are selected around Bengaluru city with various background from the age category of above 20 years. The finding was Consumer awareness of Ayurveda product influences their purchasing and Ayurveda Product Price and Brand awareness has no significant impact on Product purchase decision. Further in detail this attempt will absolutely influence aspiring researchers to work on various areas of research for the consumption and promotion of Ayurveda products across the World.

Literature Review

Based on the study of Joginder Nagar (2012), it is found that ayurveda products consumption has healed diseases like common cold, cough, allergy, constipation, joint pain, hair fall and advertisement promotions had positive impact on consumption of Ayurveda products.

Based on the study of study of Hemanth kumar (2018), it is found that consumer now are very sensible during the selection of products and especially in Gujarat state, India people are adopting Ayurveda products and switching from traditional consumption.

Based on he study of Anand Chaudhary, it is found that traditional knowledge towards Ayurveda to be explored in the international scenario should be explored and WHO is also considers this fact.

Research Methodology

Descriptive Study as the study was conducted in India with various constraints and limitation in factors considered.

Sample size: 251 respondents from the age category of 20 years and above who are consciously buying Ayurveda Products.

Convenience based sampling - a type of non-probability sampling.

Data Analysis: Structural Equation Modelling using Amos software, Factor Analysis, Confirmatory Factor analysis, regression.

Data Collection :Collected mostly qualitative data in Bangalore limits using structured questionnaire and interview using Likert scale of measurement.

Objectives

To examine the influence of awareness of Ayurveda product, awareness of price and brand image on their purchasing decision of Ayurveda products.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis1 (H1): The awareness of Ayurveda products has a no significant effect on Ayurveda Product Purchase decision

Hypothesis3 (H3): The Ayurveda products price and Brand awareness has no significant on Product purchase decision

Data Analysis

The data analysis was conducted in a three-stage process. First, reliability tests were performed. Upon satisfactory results, the factor analysis of the collected data was conducted followed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was performed to confirm the findings. SPSS Statistics 22.0 software is used to analysis the Content validity, Construct validity and Convergent validity of the model. Once the model was validated, SPSS Amos 20.0 software is used to test the overall fitness of the Structural Equation Model (SEM) and to estimate the relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable so as to accept or reject the hypothesis.

Reliability Tests

The reliability of 8 items in the questionnaire is tested with Cronbachs' alpha . If Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient is exceeding the suggested level of 0.73 It suggests that the questionnaire is having reliability and can be used for further analysis.

The cronbach's Alpha coefficient values are as follows

Exploratory Factor Analysis

The Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test is used to test suitability of data for factor analysis. KMO value was 0.727 exceeding the recommended value of 0.60 which can be considered as adequate (Kaiser and Rice, 1974) while Bartlett's Test of sphericity reached statistical significance (Approx. chi-square 531.442, df 28 and Sig 0.00) which signifies the data is good for conducting factor analysis.

The 8 items were subjected to Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation to test the suitability of data for factor analysis. The items having factor loading less than 0.50 should be eliminated (Hair et al, 1996) but all factor loading each items are above 0.50 suggesting that the data set is appropriate (Stewart, 1981). So, all 12 items are accepted and PCA revealed that these 8 items are grouped into 2 components with Eigen values exceeding 1, explaining 2.658 and 2.050 respectively. The total percentage of variance is 60.853. The individual dimensions of the proposed instrument explained total variance exceeding 60 percent, suggesting the appropriateness of the process. The results of the Principal Component Analysis can be viewed in Table1.1.

Table1.1: Factors Extraction Results of the Items in Questionnaire

Item No	Component	Eigen Value	% variance
I-Awareness of Ayurveda Product(GP)		Eigen Value	% variance
1. If consumers keep purchasing Ayurveda products, the production of Ayurveda products will eventually increase.	.778	2.658	33.229
2. Ayurveda product usually comes smaller in portion but higher in prices.	.860		
3. I'm more likely to buy Ayurveda products that are packaged in an eco-friendly manner and made easy	.806		

for recycling or composting			
II-Awareness of product Price and Brand Image (PB)		Eigen Value	% variance
1. I would choose environmentally friendly goods and services, campaigns or companies if the price were the same.	.747	2.050	25.625
2. I'm willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products.	.737		
3. If the price of Ayurveda products is less expensive I'm willing to change my lifestyle by purchasing Ayurveda products.	.745		
4. I feel more comfortable buying product from a brand that has a Ayurveda image.	.713		
5. I'm aware that a strong brand image gives me confident towards their Ayurveda product.	.702		
Total percentage of variance	60.853		

Model Fit

Based on Structure Equation Model using SPSS Amos 20 it is found that Chi-square(CMIN) = 68.424, Degree of freedom(DF) = 25 and probability level is about 0.380 which is evidence against the null hypothesis is not significant at the 0.05 level. CMIN/DF is called as the minimum discrepancy which is 1.122 Wheaton et al (1977) suggested that if the minimum discrepancy is less than 5 the model is reasonable fit.

The following value are found in our study for each parameter to test model fit

Table2: Parameter value for model fit measures with SPSS Amos.

Name of the Parameter	Value
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.950
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	0.925
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.944
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.988
Tucker-Lewis Index(TLI)	0.979
Incremental Fit Index(IFI)	0.989
Relative Fit Index(RFI)	0.901
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.028

Based on various studies it was suggested that if the Index value is greater than 0.9 and if RMSEA values is less than 0.05 it indicates model is fit and accepted.

Structure Equation Model

SPSS Amos 20 software is used to perform confirmatory factor analysis using Structural Equation Model (SEM). Total number of variables in the model is 17, number of observed variables 9, number of unobserved variables 8.

The data has no missing values. The model is over-identified, a preferable situation for SEM. According to the univariate and multivariate normality tests the data is not normally distributed. After the data was normalized, the Maximum likelihood estimation method is used. Figure 1: Structure Equation Model - The path diagram with standardized parameters estimate.

Above picture represents the path-diagram in figure1 specifies the relationship between the observed variables and unobserved variable. The CMIN/DF IS 1.122, which is less than value 5, the model fit is achieved. With that Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) value is 0.028, which is less than 0.05, so model fit is highly achieved.

In this present structural model Awareness of Ayurveda product(GP) and Awareness of Price & Brand (PB) are independent variable. The Regression weights estimates provides the relative importance. The estimates with the largest value represent the most important dimension in terms of its influence on Ayurveda product purchase decision. The findings of the regression weights estimates are summarized in table 3.1.

Table3.1: Standardized Regression weights Estimations

Factor	Direction	Factor	Estimate
Purchase Decision	←	GP-Awareness of Ayurveda product	0.189
Purchase Decision	←	PB -Awareness of Price & Brand	-0.103

P –value shows the significance of the estimation. If the P-value is less than 0.05 then there is a significant effect of the independent variable on dependent variable.

			S.E.	C.R.	P
Purchase Decision	<---	GP	.087	2.182	.029
Purchase Decision	<---	PB	.128	-0.8075	.420

Hypothesis-1: The awareness of Ayurveda product has a no significant effect on Ayurveda Product Purchase decision with standardized regression weight of 0.189 So, Hypothesis-1 is not accepted

Hypothesis-2: The Ayurveda Product Price and Brand awareness has no significant on Product purchase decision and standardized regression weight of -0.103. So, Hypothesis- 2 is accepted.

Findings and Conclusion

Based on the study and data analysis conducted in this research, it can be stated that, consumers' awareness of Ayurveda product does influence their purchasing decision. Consumers' awareness of price and brand image does not influence their purchasing decision. Moreover, the proposed model fit is accepted statistical, in continuation with the structural equation modeling, it is found that Ayurveda Product awareness is creating significant impact amongst respondents. Pricing has less impact or no impact on purchase decision.

So it is suggested that awareness of Ayurveda Product should be increased to ease the consumption and price should be decreased to some extent, to increase the overall sales of Ayurveda Products.

References

1. Arya, Vikrant & Thakur, Raneev & Kumar, Suresh & Kumar, Sanjeev. (2012). Consumer buying behaviour towards ayurvedic medicines/ products in joginder nagar- a survey. *Ayurpharm - International Journal of Ayurveda and Allied Sciences*. 1. 60-64.
2. Bulsara, H. P., & Yadav, N. (2018). A Study on the Current Scenario of Consumers Buying Behavior towards Ayurvedic Medicines In Gujarat. 5.
3. Chaudhary, A., & Singh, N. (2011). Contribution of world health organization in the global acceptance of Ayurveda. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*, 2(4), 179–186. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0975-9476.90769>.
4. Mishra SP, Semwal DK, Chauhan A. Scenario of Ayurveda education in India: Some recommendations for development. *University News – Association of Indian Universities*. 2015; 53:3–8.
5. Bombardieri D, Easthope G. Convergence between orthodox and alternative medicine: A theoretical elaboration and empirical test. *Health*. 2000;4:479–94.
6. Ayurvedic research and methodology: Present status and future strategies, AYU, *International Quarterly Journal of Research in Ayurveda*, 2015 Oct-Dec; 36(4): 364–369.
7. The Financial Express (Washington ed.). 24 August 2012. 9 December 2014.
8. Sheth, J.N., "History of Consumer Behavior: a Marketing Perspective", in *Historical Perspective in Consumer Research: National and International Perspectives*, Jagdish N. Sheth and Chin Tiong Tan (eds), Singapore, Association for Consumer Research, 1985, pp 5-7.